

Descriptive statistics showing Number of participant by region

Region	Number	Mean ± STD
St Petersburg	60	0,93 ± 0,67
Kaluga	40	3,18 ± 1.22
Moscow	73	0,75 ± 1.15
UFA	40	2,51 ± 1.80
Vladimir	40	3,26 ± 0.45
Vladivostok	40	1,90 ± 1.49
Tomsk	40	0,63 ± 0.77
Other regions (Norilsk and Murmansk)	67	0,67 ± 0.47
Total	400	

Descriptive statistics showing mean ± standard deviation and variance of all Variables

Variables	Mean ± Standard Deviation	Variance
Age	2,43 ± 1,58	2,50
Gender	0,17 ± 0,38	0,15
Occupation	3,28 ± 2,44	5,95
Region	3,28 ± 2,51	6,29
OATECIYH	1,54 ± 1,47	2,19
FIYHEC	1,05 ± 1,03	1,06
HIIEETYWPNA	1,58 ± 0,84	0,72
DYBTRECCPITE	1,08± 1,19	1,42
HODYDECWFM	3,43 ± 0,49	0,25
WIYHMIR	1,71± 1,01	1,03
HMPLIYH	0,28 ± 0,45	0,20
HLOEABAMOYH	2,29 ± 0,64	0,41
DYSSIYCOEEA	0,57± 0,49	0,25
HYMACTRECDFC	0,59 ± 0,49	0,24
ATSCBOPIYCTAHYUEAH	0,45 ± 0,49	0,25
HDTPIYCIYHATEU	0,18 ± 0,39	0,15
DYTCATCACIR	1,22 ± 0,99	0,98
TWEDSGOCEIYHEC	0,27 ± 0,45	0,19
AYAOAGIAAPEEIH	0,47 ± 0,50	0,25
HDYLATI	1,50 ± 1,15	1,33
OASF1T5HWYRYKAETAP	3,22 ± 1,26	1,61
HYPIAWOPFOIEEAH	0,34 ± 0,47	0,23
WYBIILMAHTIEEIIYH	1,66 ± 1,52	2,32

Key:

OATECIYH: overall attitude towards energy consumption in your household

FIYHEC: factors influence your household's energy consumption

HIIEETYWPNA: How important is energy efficiency to you when purchasing new appliances?

DYBTRECCPITE: Do you believe that reducing energy consumption can positively impact the environment?

HODYDECWFM: How often do you discuss energy consumption with family members

WIYHMIR: What is your household's monthly income range?

HMPLIYH: How many people live in your household

HLOEABAMOYH: highest level of education attained by any member of your household

DYSSICYOEEA: Does your socio-economic status influence your choice of energy-efficient appliances?

HYMACTRECDFC: Have you made any changes to reduce energy consumption due to financial constraints?

ATSCBOPIYCTAHYUEAH: Are there specific cultural beliefs or practices in your community that affect how you use energy at home?

HDTPIYCIYHATEU: How do traditional practices in your culture influence your household's approach to energy usage?

DYTCATCACIR: Do you think cultural attitudes towards conservation are changing in Russia?

TWEDSGOCEIYHEC: To what extent do social gatherings or community events impact your household's energy consumption patterns?

AYAOAGIAAPEEIH: Are you aware of any government initiatives aimed at promoting energy efficiency in households?

HDYLATI: How did you learn about these initiatives?

OASF1T5HWYRYKAETAP: On a scale from 1 to 5 how would you rate your knowledge about energy-saving technologies and practices?

HYPIAWOPFOIEEAH: Have you participated in any workshops or programs focused on improving energy efficiency at home?

WYBIILMAHTIEEIIYH: Would you be interested in learning more about how to improve energy efficiency in your home?